

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES FUNCTIONALITY IN MUSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

As a result of improvement of computer technologies, the musical culture, as a part of humanity one, appears to be in turning moment. At this stage of musical education there is important to be created conditions for smooth transition to modern technologies without rejecting or neglecting the existing traditional methods and tools for education. The effective usage of computer equipment is defined by three interrelated aspects: technical, methodological and organizational. Achievement of balance among them ensures realization of the three basic functions of information computer technologies (ICT) in musical education: informational, thematic and creative-simulation. Technical insurance already is implemented and it is supported by informational function but organizational and methodical implementation of technologies is behind that is preventing introduction of thematic and creative-simulation functions of information computer technologies.

Keywords: musical, technology, software, functions, thematic, creative-simulation

Introduction

New stage in social development is the transition from information society to society of knowledge [4]. This transition strongly influences the processes of education. Characteristics of the society of knowledge is the changing of inlet and outlet factors as well as the processes occurring in there and infrastructures related to creation of new value of the knowledge. It besides the factor called information includes also intellectual (effective implementation of the knowledge for resolving of specific problems).

Extremely fast development of computer technologies and also from the point of view from technical specification as well as cumbersome realization of servicing systems (including educational software) bring our attention to existing already attractive and updated resources that support educational process. They do not create didactic contradiction between the process of education and applied approaches. Priority in the musical education is the equal realization of the three basic functions of information computer technologies (ICT): informational, thematic, and creative simulative. For their realizations are important technical, methodological and organizational aspects of implementation of the technologies, their interconnection and dependence from the socio-economic environment. The very fast rate of computer technologies development that contradicts to the cumbersome development of the servicing systems bring our attention to existing school projects that have goals implementation of the necessary foundation to the entrance of the new technologies. However, there is still missing clear concept for organization and methods of their implementation in the musical education.

Theoretical basis

The strong presence of the computer into the contemporary human daily life of contemporary men faces its using as information tool that have fast and easy access to facts and data of any kind. The educational system reacts adequate to the socio economical changes and more often uses ICT as string informational tool for

reaching of the base goals. In the case of musical equation and revealing of the nature of musical art through computer technologies there is needed equilibrium presence of informational thematic and creative simulative functions of ICT. The role of information al function is closed in establishing of information flow that related to particular topics and implemented in dialog contacts between student-computer and teacher computer. In this case there are used multimedia products, presentation software, electronic textbooks that bring the educational content using the resources of as example Macromedia, Adobe Flash Player, MS Power Point and etc. Foundation for this is the interactive and synthesized presentation of discussed topic. Multimedia translation of musical information is especially effective when is needed to be adopted a new concept; visualization or to look for realization of creativeness in though – intellectual activity, based on the selection and organization of informational package. Information function is primary and in this stage of implementation of ICT in musical education finds the widest usage. The software that can be used is more universal and has capability to be implemented in all areas of educational system. Its implementation in musical class teaching can form flexible and attractive system for information transferring.

The thematic function of ICT is related to implementation of particular information in cognitive activity. It is implemented in educational software adapted to particular ages of school students and school content, created for targeting servicing of NES (national educational standards) and related to informational standards. Despite that there is still missing overall system for musical education, based on computer technologies, experimental works in this direction are dated from 1950 year when is created the first educational software [17, p.119]. “Historically one of the first educational uses made of computer technology was in the United States for Computer-Assisted Instruction (CAI). As the term ‘instruction’ implies, the student was taught a particular skill or knowledge by a computer ei-

ther through a computerised programmed learning situation (generally an interactive tutorial-with-testing type lesson), or for situations where rote learning was deemed to be appropriate, through a drill-and-practice-type program” [1, p.24-26]. In 1972 year in University of Minnesota D. Gross [5, p.35-42] developed many computer programs the contained exercises in the theory of music and solmization (developing of rhythmic hearing, finding of harmonic consequence and recording under musical dictation). In 1973 scientific team from Stanford University [11, p.89-101] made an experiment for implementation of computers in developing of hearing habits. In 1974 in University of Delaware [8] was created automated teaching system GUIDO that is targeting forming of hearing habits. The Graded Units for Interactive Dictation Operations, or G.U.I.D.O., was the first ear-training “software” developed in the mid 1970s using the PLATO mainframe to provide programmed instruction for the recognition of intervals, melodies, chords harmonies and rhythms for college music students. During 80-s the problem of computerization of musical education is analyzed form the position of didactical factors, and positive results are reported in implementation of software technologies in musical computer technologies. In this period there is created significant amount of educational software. Hess [7, p.7] described and educational experiment in University of North Colorado where a computer program was used for formation of hearing habits for the first year university students. Orphen [13, p.67-70] also commented results from studies of implementation of training software in formation of rhythmic habits in high school students in middle musical school. Timoty Smigh also created “7th Chord Identification”

and “7th Chord construction” [17, p.142]. From all these studies we can conclude that only isolated cases are looking for and consider generalized problems of musical education computerization.

As results from development of technical specifications of ICT there can be separated five categories musical software based products with thematically oriented functions: instructing, training, playing researching and creative. The instructing software is created as a number of teaching lessons. Inside them is implemented text, audio computer graphics, animation targeting bringing knowledge and abilities. They offer theoretical questions for studying. The problems and questions are organized in software as dialog interface for human – machine interaction to manage an educational procedure. Such programs are Easy Guitar, Easy Piano, History of Jazz [7], Music Ace [6], Music Ace2 [6] Multimedia Music Theory [http://plchoristers.org/multimedia/theory.php4 , n.d.]. *The training programs* are targeting development of hearing habits and training of hear perception. Most known such software is: Auralia, Early Music Skills, MiBAC Music Lessons, Musition and Music Lab Melody [17, p.132-133]. The gaming software is developed for younger users, where in gaming process is targeting giving of basic musical knowledge. The research software is related to studying of important events and facts in development of music. The main focus is directed to history of musical art. Creative functions provoke into creation of a product. By them there can be added arrangement, changed a style of a work of music. Such programs are Making Music, Band in a Box. Table No. 1 presents the capabilities of different scientific software with thematic functions. (CAI-Computer Assisted Instruction).

Table I

Types of CAI and implementation possibilities in the pedagogical process

		TYPES OF CAI				
		Training	Instructing	Gaming	Researching	Creating
Possibilities for forming functional music literacy	Basic musical skills	Early Music Skills	Music Ace I	Menlo the Frog		Making Music
	Listening skills and theory of music	Music Lab MiBAC Music Lessons	Music Ace II	Musicus, Julliard Music Adventure		
	History of music	Music Terminology	Discovering Music	Xplora I Pianist	Apple Pie, Classical Notes, Living Jazz	Enhanced CD, Crazy for Rag
	musical performance	Rhythm Tutor		Piano, Teach Me piano		SmartMusic
	Composing and improvising					Band in a Box Sound Toys Making More Music

Creativeness simulative function of ICT can be also found in software that affords creation of a product from cognitive activity of the students. This function is

realized through specialized musical software. Specialized musical software is a complex tool. It can be used for practical and theoretical preparation. There is given practical and theoretical knowledge for the nature of

musical theory. In parallel is created a system of actions that are necessary in creation of musical product. It can be used as servicing tool in process of creation: composing, arranging, music processing. Capabilities for working with specialized software are foundation for development of conscious and motivated activity in music area. Computer, equipped with specialized software is a new type musical instrument. Its primary advantage is availability and ability to be used by any user, where base on the principle of individualization, the user can take any decision in dependence from his interests, personalization and motivation to what level he intends to adopt musical matter. Specialized software is very complexity because there is a perspective in studying and mastering. The specialized software can be separated in three categories: notating, sound editors and sequencers. The software applied for educational purposes is the same as the one used for recording of new musical album or a new advertising. It has multiple functions. Its advantage appears in significant database of facts and information. This makes the activities related to musical theory significantly accessible and implemented in the software helps plan sequence of actions necessary for completion of given tasks. Capabilities that have application of specialized

software are endless. Depending on the educational goals can be selected the appropriate software or selected functions/options of programs that can serve target pursuing component.

The specificity and uniqueness of the musical lesson is supported by thematic and creativeness functions. More complicated from technical, methodological and organizational aspect is implementation of these two function in musical education in Bulgarian low and middle school. In the United States and Germany even in the middle of the last century began methodological and organizational preparation for implementation of computer software technologies in educational system. Independently from the hardware changes, that follows the computer in its development, the methodical and organizational aspects are adapted in parallel with technical evolution.

Implementation of informational, thematic and creative-simulation functions helps the pedagogical, educational and developing functions of educational process. In fig. 1 is presented the relation between aspects of implementation of ICT, functions and goal-pursuing component by education through computer technologies.

Figure 1. Correlation and aspects of CAI implementation, functions and goal directing component

All of these functions is needed by technical, methodological and organizational support. Engagement of educational system is organization and methodological support. Engagement of socio-economic environment is technical. When defining the goals of musical education, through computer technologies application finds the new taxonomy by Marzano [12]. In his work, he accounts the changes that appear in society and adopts ICT as tool for transformation of inert knowledge in real applied in life processes. In his taxonomy, he includes three systems and area of our knowledge. The three systems are **I-system, cognitive system and system of meta-cognition**. These systems are in constant coordination with the area of

knowledge. In situation when appear a new possibility I-system decides to continue the current line of behavior or to begins new activity. The system of meta-cognition (thinking) establishes the goals and follows their archiving. Cognitive system analyzes the information and area of knowledge gives the necessary content. All three systems are in direct dependence from the functions of application of ICT in education. Smooth transition from informative to thematic and creative-simulative allows pedagogical goal-placing to follow the logical structure: cognitive, meta-cognitive and I-system.

The structure of cognitive system is divided on four components: getting knowledge, understanding,

analysis and usage. Computer software keeper of information function completely support and create conditions for effective work of cognitive system but does not support the realization of metacognitive system. It manages all brain processes of thinking and has regulatory function to remaining systems. In there are established the goals and there are taking decisions about the importance of the information and cognitive processes for achieving.

Metacognitive system consists from definitions of educational goals; monitoring of knowledge implementation, understanding and accuracy. In this system are included all brain processes that are subordinated to the educational goal. That are all processes, related with internal plan and choice of strategies of the educating person for cognitive activity. The categories of musical computer based products with thematic functions form the components of metacognitive system and help for activating of I-system.

I-system consists from relations, conviction and feelings that define the motivation of a single person for completion of a given task and cooperation of the basis of personal interests and motivation in the area of knowledge. To the factor of motivation can be related: effectiveness and emotions. The meaning is interrelated with the importance of a single person of the matter that is studied. Effectiveness in I-system is shown from the point of view of a single person and is related with the conviction that the given goal can be achieved by the capabilities of subject of education. Working with specialized software the students are introduced to contemporary tools for treatment and creation of musical pieces. There are implemented the achievements in musical art. In parallel there are simulated real processes of creation and arrangement of musical piece. This brings the persons under education in problematic situation that requires thinking about the problem and taking of a decision. Implementation of a particular input information approaches a real meaning in practice and if the interest to music as art is durable than the corresponding student could deepens and expands in time but for this purpose, he may need a personal computer equipped with a special musical software. Working with specialized musical software in classroom, the educational activity is getting closer to art practicing, enriching of a timbre hearing and imagination for the tone capabilities. There also is ongoing optimization of the all kind of hearing analyses with support by the vision perception.

Objectivized the management of the trained persons activities and results can be followed. After the usage of specialized software there can be observed patterns of musical morphology and syntax. There also can be developed habits for orientation in intonation-semantic level of perception and awareness of contend - imagination plans of musical work. The emotions that are related with the education can show big influence in trainee's motivation. Computer and the corresponding software are based on system of axioms and algorithms that presents database of knowledge i.e. they constantly enlarge the information in dependence of

deepening of cognitive activity. In this case, the architecture of goal – placing corresponds the best with the taxonomy of targets by Marzano [12]

In chart 1 is seen that the smallest resource is servicing information function of ICT in musical education. There is no necessary changes in methodological and organization aspects but the computer is transformed in a tool by which is modernized and updated the traditional presentation of school content. The application of information function is basic for thematic and creative simulative function. Besides, it supports metacognitive and I-systems. However, it should not have leading role in musical education. The uniqueness of music as art is based on hearing- motorized imagination and the development of musical abilities. For this to occur, the student must be active but not a passive subject in musical activities. The meaning of application of ICT in musical education can be discovered only within created conditions for individualization of education in the environment of public educational system. The software that brings thematic and creativeness simulative function create the ability to be realized the process of creation and to be activated emotional responsiveness. The technical aspect is also very important. At the first place, each high school student must have individual working place equipped with the necessary software and headphones.

The organization aspect has a leading function because it includes analysis of educational programs, selection of method and creation of products that serve goal-pacing component. In Bulgaria, there is a lack of programs with thematic functions and this fact directs the searching of musical pedagogue toward educational resources in other countries. There is an impression that the logical structure of the software is following the didactic principles. In internet exist several products that can be used free of charge [2]. These are thematic educational games based on platform Macromedia Flash Player 6. Some of the free of charge products are "Alice in Vivaldi's Four Seasons" , "Orchestra" [2] and etc. The software, developed by "InteractiveClassics" informational and thematic functions are didactically related with software where appear the same elements. As example in the game "Orchestra" and multimedia encyclopedia "Mozart 250" [2]. The game "Orchestra" has a goal to introduce the pupils in the basic musical instruments and their timbres. Given sound problems, the pupils must find the musical instrument by mouse clicking at its picture. If the answer is wrong, a gong signal appears. In case of correct answer, the musical instrument alone with its instrumentalist takes corresponding position in the orchestra. The instrumentalists are resented as animated animals that appear in the remaining games, created by the same team [2]. By this approach is created a series of products serving different purposes of musical education. The gaming interface is very simple. The game "Orchestra" can be played by children of age from four to 12. The interest of pupils to this product is significant. They easily learn, playing fun at the same time with the musical instruments timbres. After ordering of all elements of the game successful completion is indicated by playing of Mozart's "The Magic Flute" ("Die Zauberflöte"), K.

620. Several repetitions of the cognitive interface of the gaming product helps to be remembered the musical content [15]. Creation and application of such thematic products can have significant impact and optimization of the process of learning in music.

Three aspects of application of ICT in education are important for creativeness simulation function but the leading one is the methodological. The software implemented in educational system is the same as the used by professional musicians for composing, arranging and recording. Musical pedagogue performs the selection of the particular software and its adaptation for the purposes of education. His responsibility appears in structuration of methodological system for application of the corresponding musical technology in education. We discovered enormous gap in application of creativeness simulative function of ICT in musical education. It appears in contrasting highest level of technical development and breaking away of the methodological and organizational aspects for application. From chart No. 1 it is clearly seen that for completely application is important systematic and consistent way to be applied the technological functions in educational system. Only after all this ICT can be interpreted as educational-developing environment for creativeness and self-teaching of high school students. The cognitive, meta-cognitive and I systems are closely interrelated form the three functions of the application of ICT in musical education. There is very important for musical education formation to be formed need of communication with musical art. Realization of the importance for a single personality most significantly is formed during the process of creativeness. The application of specialized musical software allows the musical matter to be transformed in individual experience.

Models of implementation of thematic and creativeness simulative functions

Since 2004 in Simon Bolivar School, (Plovdiv, Bulgaria) were tested three functions of ICT. The attention is directed toward thematic and creativeness simulative. In the first years were studied information functions but in the process of work was concluded that this model of education does not fit the requirements for full implementation of technologies in musical education. Even more, the information technologies entered all educational areas the reduced the attractiveness musical-pedagogical searching in this direction. That forced studies of musical software. There is significant diversity of the software with thematic functions. Most often, virtual keyboards are used. They allow playing of musical theme; composing of music, help in following of the tone pitch and revising of meaning of musical symbols. Currently exist some freeware that can fit these capabilities. In addition to described above games of Interactive Classics, in the process of education can be applied also published in website [3] resources. The game Compose Your Own Music was used in lower

high school grades teaching (third and fourth grades). The students were requested to make a musical piece consisting from four cadences in size 4/4. There were expected to use the default software notation durations. The product allows to be listen and corrected the recorded as well as to be send by electronic mail the completed product through the interface button send to my friend. The next stage of the activity is the analysis of errors, discussion and listening of the most interesting melodies. Here we registered very high activities and interest from the participants.

For most effective realization of creativeness simulative function in musical education there is important to be developed a methodic system and to be selected specialized software the will serve educational goals. The Simon Bolivar school were tested two musical systems where one of them was targeting activation perception of musical piece while the other was targeting metro-rhythmical accompaniment on the selected musical theme.

The fist system was implemented with two computer programs: notating software and sequencer. Methodic system of perception of musical piece includes five stages:

Score creation with the help of notation software after insertion of the main theme of the musical piece.

Listening of notated record in software environment and correction of discovered errors.

Listening the entire musical work and finding there the recorded theme by notes.

Cutting the theme with the help of MIDI sequencer.

Arranging of the musical theme by preliminary prepared samples and beates, implemented in the sequencer.

There were used demo versions of notating software Sibelius [16] and sequencer FLStudio 5 [10]. In the experiment were participating sixth grade students. The experimental masterwork was Petko Stainov's "Paydoushko" from Symphonic suite "Thracian dances" (1925-1926). After analysis of obtained results by qualitative and quantitative methods for information collection, we found that the experimental group had significantly higher results than the control group that followed the classical teaching approach [14, 383-389].

For analyses of the results after the performed study with sound problem is used ANOVA. The comparison is performed by the average results. The obtained data at 5% level of significance ($F=11,259$, $p<0.0007$), shown in the table below, demonstrate that the controlled group No. 1, controlled group No. 2 and the experimental group are different. This difference between the groups is statistically significant. From the diagram there is seen that the experimental group gives highest results in this study.

Statistical analysis of data after a study performance

ANOVA					
Result: "Paydushko horo"					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	16,489	2	8,245	11,259	,000
Within Groups	43,205	59	,732		
Total	59,694	61			

Figure 2 Achievements of controlled group (1 u 2) and experimental (3)

The tested methodic system for creation of metro-rhythmical accompaniment to musical theme includes three stages:

- Listening of musical theme and portions analysis.
- Selection of percussions.
- Creation of accompaniments.

There was used MuseScore (<https://musescore.org/bg>) freeware. Participants in this experiment were fifth grade high school students. The goal of this lesson was confirmation of musical theme; shaping and type of percussions. All of the students were using the software for the first time. All working places were supplied with "Variation on a theme" by W. A. Mozart (fig. 3). The main task is to

listen the musical record and to find musical sentences. After analysis of the structure of the theme must be revealed the algorithm and added the percussions. There is condition no more than four percussions must be added. In the process of work the student attention is directed to the second sequence, where the character is different and it will be better if the accompaniment corresponds to the mood. As the working places in information technologies cabinet is only 12, then the students worked in team by two. Every team worked separately. The teacher appeared only as mediator, helping the process. We did not find student that showed difficulties to the way how the data is structured in MuseScore.

Figure 3. Implementation of MuseScore in educational process

Conclusion.

Implementation of ICT in musical education creates conditions for realization more flexible educational system in music where the goals are related with particular activities. It helps with achieving of better results in educational-cognitive area. It also creates conditions for self-teaching in musical art. There is very important the application not to be chaotic answer of searching in socio-economic environment but substantiated pedagogical act. Therefore, the priorities of musical education must be enforced in application computer technologies.

References:

1. Stevens, R. S. (1991). The Best of Both Worlds: An Eclectic Approach to the Use of Computer Technology in Music Education. *Int. J. Music Education*, 17, 24-36.
2. Tigor Media Inc. (2005-2017). Retrieved from <http://www.interactiveclassics.com>.
3. Cincinnati Public Radio . (2018). Retrieved from <http://www.classicsforkids.com>.
4. Drucker, P. F. (1994). *Post-Capitalist Society*. New York: HarperCollins.
5. Gross, D. (1984). Computer applications to music theory: a retrospective. *Computer Music Journal*, 8(4), 35-42.
6. Harmonic Vision Inc. (2013). Retrieved from <http://www.harmonicvision.com/> 12.02.2017.
7. Hess, G. J. (1994). Strategies for Integrating Computer-Based Training in College Music Theory Courses - June 25-30]. *World Conference on Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia* (p. 7). (Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada,; University of Northern Colorado.
8. Hofstetter, F. T. (1975). GUIDO: an interactive computer-based system for improvement of instruction and research in ear-training. *Journal of Computer-Based Instruction*, 1(4), 100-106.
9. <http://plchoristers.org/multimedia/theory.php4> . (n.d.).
10. Image Line Software . (2004, November 22). Retrieved from http://www.image-line.com/flstudio/history.php?entry_id=1287145936.
11. Kuhn, W. E. (1974). Computer-assisted Instruction in Music: Drill and Practice in Dictation. *College Music Symposium* 14,, 14, 89-101.
12. Marzano, R. J. (2000). *Designing a New Taxonomy of Education Objectives* . Thousand Oaks: Corwin Press.
13. Orthen, J. M. (1995). The Effectiveness of a Computer-Assisted Instruction Program in Rhythm for Secondary School Instrumental Students. (dissertation review) . *Bulletin of the Council for Research in Music Education*, 124, 67-70.
14. Petkova, D. V. (2011). Stimulation of the process of creativeness through specialized musical software during musical classes in the middle school in Bulgaria. *Education and technologies*, 383-389.
15. Petkova, D. V. (2013). Application of Computer Technologies in Music Education in Secondary School in Bulgaria. *Doktorantska Akademia*.
16. Spreadbury , D., Finn, B., & Finn, J. (2011). *Sibelius 7, Reference Guide, Edition 7.1, November*. USA: Avid Technology, Inc.
17. Williams, D. B., & Webster, P. R. (1999). *Experiencing Music Tehnology: Software, Data, and Hardware*. New York: Schirmer.